

SOCIAL SUPPORT AND MATERNAL HEALTH OUTCOMES IN CALABAR METROPOLIS, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Social support is a key determinant of maternal health, influencing prenatal care, pregnancy outcomes, and postpartum recovery. This study examined the relationship between social support and maternal health outcomes in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State, Nigeria, using a quantitative design with 385 respondents selected through random and purposive sampling. Data were analyzed with descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings showed that only 53% of women were aware of available support systems, reflecting gaps in health education and information dissemination. Friends (21.6%) and husbands/partners (20.8%) were the main support providers, while family, community, and religious groups played lesser roles. Strengthening these networks is essential to improving maternal well-being.

Keywords: Social Support, Maternal Health.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is generally viewed as a period that is filled with various physiological and emotional changes and these changes tend to have significant effects on maternal health outcomes (McLeish and Redshaw 2017) During this period, close relations and other individuals play an integral role in influencing the quality of life of expectant mothers by providing physical and emotional support to the pregnant woman (McLeish and Redshaw 2017). This assistance is termed social support. As espoused by Ademuyiwa et al., (2020) social support is the provision of assistance or comfort to other people to help them cope with a variety of problems. The support usually comes from interpersonal relationships, family members, neighbours, support groups, religious groups and friends. Studies have reported a correlation between social support and maternal health outcomes in different social settings. Social support has been reported to play a crucial role in maternal health and wellbeing. In their view, Nazari et al, (2015) in Ademuyiwa et al (2020) argue that people who have a high level of social support are more likely to have better health behaviour and outcomes, such as increased use of preventive health services, than those who have low support birth companionship. It has a crucial influence on maternal health and well-being during pregnancy and it is expected to promote positive well-being, subsequently resulting in expectant mothers perceiving

pregnancy-related changes as less stressful (Mabetha, 2022). Social support has also been reported to have positive effects during labour and postpartum. It also helps in reducing women's risk of developing postnatal depression and improved health through breastfeeding (Saghooni et al., 2020). Tani and Castagna (2017) acknowledged that social support positively influences labour and is a protective factor against depression.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Statistics revealed that at least, one in every thirteen Nigerian women dies during pregnancy or childbirth, and this is more prevalent in the rural population, where there are fewer health facilities. According to the WHO (2019) report, about 295,000 women died as a result of pregnancy and childbirth related issues in the year 2017; majority (94%) of these deaths occurred in low-and middle-income countries. Regrettably, some of these deaths could have been prevented with social support. World Health Organization (2019), reports further that 86% of maternal deaths were from Sub-Saharan Africa. Southern Asia and sub-Saharan Africa alone accounted for two-thirds of maternal deaths. Nigeria is currently among the 15 countries with 'very high alert' or 'high alert' with maternal mortality rates (MMR). Overall, studies have further shown that socio-cultural dynamics elicit different perceptions about spousal support during pregnancy. In Nigeria, patriarchal culture ensures that the decisions on the kind of health facilities to consult even during pregnancy mostly rest on the male counterparts, especially husbands. The prevailing patriarchal system in rural areas explains this. Currently, 48.8% of the population of Nigeria is rural (99,027,063 people in 2020), among whom about 45% are women. Considering the predominance of the patriarchal and polygamous systems that characterise rural communities in Nigeria, it is pertinent to examine the social support experiences of urban women during pregnancy, labour, and delivery.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to examine lived experiences and the effects of social support on maternal health outcome in Calabar Metropolis and to suggest a better blueprint for social support and maternal health. The specific objectives are as follows

To identify the types of social support obtainable among of pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis.

To examine social support and experiences of pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis

To ascertain health implications of social support on the health of women

To identify and suggest strategies for improving social support and maternal health

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions have been designed to guide this study?

What are the types of social support obtainable among of pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis?

What are the social support experience of pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis?

What is the health implication of social support on the health of women?

What are the strategies for improving social support and health of women?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

Stress Model Theory

The stress model theory by Lazarus and Folkman (1984) emphasized the interplay between an individual's perceived psychological stress, coping, and cognitive assessments. This perspective is an effective framework for understanding how social support influence maternal health outcomes. Pregnancy presents multiple stressors, physical, financial, and emotional that may be appraised as threats or challenges. Social support influences this appraisal by enhancing coping capacity, reducing perceived stress, and promoting better health behaviours. Strong networks offer emotional, informational, and practical assistance, fostering maternal well-being and positive mental health, which are essential for both mother and child.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The Quantitative research design was adopted for this study. This design is used in research to collect, analyze, and interpret numerical data.

Research area

Cross River State is a coastal State in Southern Nigeria. Calabar Metropolis, the capital of Cross River State, is located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It comprises two Local Government Areas (LGAs): Calabar Municipal and Calabar South.

Population of Study

The target population for this study included all pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis, Cross River State.

Sample Size

The sample size for this study is three hundred and ninety eight (398) respondents. It was determined using the Cochran (1963) formula. This study used the infinite formula which is used when the accurate population is unknown.

Sampling Techniques

This study made use of a combination of simple random sampling and purposive sampling to ensure a representative yet focused selection of participants. Simple random sampling was used to recruit mothers from healthcare facilities, while purposive sampling was applied to include specific subgroups of interest, such as adolescent mothers. For the simple random sampling, a list of pregnant and postpartum women receiving maternal healthcare services in selected hospitals and maternity clinics was obtained. From this list, participants were randomly selected using a lottery method, ensuring each eligible individual had an equal chance of participation. This approach minimized selection bias and enhanced the generalizability of the findings. Purposive sampling was used to recruit specific groups that required targeted investigation. These included adolescent mothers, as they may have unique social support needs. Healthcare professionals assisted in identifying these participants based on predefined inclusion criteria.

Instrumentation

This study adopted the quantitative method for data collection to examine the relationship between social support and maternal health outcomes. The quantitative data collection was done using a researcher-developed questionnaire.

Methods of Data Analysis

The quantitative data collected was processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) statistical software. Analysis was done using frequency tables and percentages.

RESULT

In this study, questionnaire was administered on 385 women within the study area. Out of the 398 questionnaire copies distributed to the respondents, only 385 copies (representing 96.7% of the distributed questionnaire copies) were returned; while 13 copies (representing 3.3% of the distributed questionnaire copies) were lost in the field.

Demographic Analysis

This section contains the descriptive analysis and interpretation of quantitative data collected from the field.

Table 1
Demographic Analysis of Respondents

Parameters	Categories	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	15-20	92	23.9
	21-30	93	24.2
	31-40	106	27.5
	41 and above	94	24.4
Marital Status	Divorced	100	26.0
	Married	88	22.9
	Single	107	27.8
	Widowed	90	23.4
Educational Level	No Formal Education	76	19.7
	Primary Education	97	25.2
	Secondary Education	114	29.6
	Tertiary Education	98	25.5
Occupation	Government Worker	84	21.8

	Private Sector Employee	94	24.4
	Self-employed	115	29.9
	Unemployed	92	23.9
Number of Children	1	98	25.5
	2	93	24.2
	3	98	25.5
	More than 3	96	24.9

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Respondents were fairly evenly distributed across age groups, with the largest proportion aged 31–40 years (27.5%). Marital status showed higher representation of single (27.8%) and divorced (26.0%) individuals, while widowed (23.4%) and married (22.9%) respondents were slightly fewer. Most had secondary (29.6%) and tertiary (25.5%) education, with smaller proportions having primary (25.2%) and (19.7%) with no formal education. Occupationally, self-employment was most common (29.9%), followed by private sector (24.4%), unemployment (23.9%), and government work (21.8%). Parity was also balanced, with most respondents having one to three children.

Social Support types and Experience amongst Respondents

The awareness of respondents concerning the idea of social support is recorded in displayed in figure 1. 205 (53%) of the respondents are aware of social support for pregnant women and nursing mothers, whereas 180 (47%).

Table 2
Sources/Providers of Support Received by Respondent Pregnant Women and Nursing Mothers

Support Type	Frequency	Percentage
Community/Religious Groups	75	19.5
Family Members	75	19.5
Friends	83	21.6
Healthcare Workers	72	18.7
Husband/Partner	80	20.8

Source: Field survey, 2025

Analysis of support sources showed that friends (21.6%) and husbands/partners (20.8%) were the main providers, followed by family and community/religious groups (19.5% each). Healthcare workers contributed 18.7%, indicating that while professional support is important, social and familial networks remain the dominant sources of maternal support.

Types of Social Support

Financial support was most common (26.8%), followed by physical (25.5%), and emotional/informational support (23.9% each). Satisfaction levels were mixed: 41.1% were satisfied, 38.1% dissatisfied, and 20.8% neutral.

Figure 3 presents respondents' levels of satisfaction with the social support they received. Satisfaction with social support was mixed: 41.1% of respondents reported being satisfied or very satisfied, 20.8% were neutral, and 38.1% expressed dissatisfaction. Overall, perceptions were evenly distributed, with a slight tilt toward positive or neutral views.

Figure 4: Consistency of social support received by respondents. Support was inconsistent, with 25.7% reporting no consistency, 24.9% receiving it always or sometimes, and 24.4% rarely. These findings highlight irregular access to social support among respondents.

Figure 5: Response to ever experience of Neglect at least once in the past

Over half of respondents (54%) reported experiencing neglect during pregnancy, which may adversely affect mental health, stress levels, and health-seeking behaviours, potentially contributing to depression and reduced well-being.

Health Implications of Social Support on the Health of Women

Over half of respondents (54%) were unaware of the health implications of social support, while 46% were aware. Perceptions of its impact were mixed: 42.1% agreed that strong support improves outcomes, 39.2% disagreed, and 18.7% were neutral. Reported benefits included improved healthcare access (25.2%), reduced stress (24.4%), and enhanced emotional well-being (21.3%), though 29.1% perceived no effect.

Figure 6: Respondent’s awareness of the Health Implications of Social Support

Figure 7: Respondent opinion on the idea that women with strong social support experience better health outcome

Figure 8: Response to the influence of support on health of respondent
Strategies for Improving Social Support of Pregnant Women

The respondents identified several strategies to enhance social support for pregnant women and nursing mothers as seen in table 3.

Table 3
Respondents’ response to Strategies for Improving Social Support of Pregnant Women

Response	Frequency	Percentage
What do you think can be done to improve social support for pregnant women and nursing mothers?		
Community and religious group support	89	23.1
Government policies supporting maternal care	108	28.1
Increased family involvement	93	24.2
More awareness on maternal health issues	95	24.7

How can healthcare services be improved for better maternal health outcomes?

Free or affordable maternity services	93	24.2
Increased government funding for maternal care	89	23.1
More trained healthcare professionals	103	26.8
Public health campaigns on maternal well-being	100	26.0

How can healthcare services be improved for better maternal health outcomes?

Free or affordable maternity services	93	24.2
Increased government funding for maternal care	89	23.1
More trained healthcare professionals	103	26.8
Public health campaigns on maternal well-being	100	26.0

Key strategies suggested to enhance maternal support included government policies (28.1%), increased health awareness (24.7%), family involvement (24.2%), and active roles for community/religious groups (23.1%). For healthcare improvements, respondents emphasized more trained professionals (26.8%), public health campaigns (26.0%), affordable maternity services (24.2%), and greater government funding (23.1%).

Discussion of findings

Findings reveal gaps in awareness and utilization of social support among pregnant women and nursing mothers, with only 53% reporting knowledge of available systems. Limited awareness may stem from inadequate health education, poor information dissemination, and cultural barriers (Yihune Teshale et al., 2025; Penman et al., 2023; Dahab & Sakellariou, 2020). Friends were the most cited source of support (21.6%), followed by husbands/partners (20.8%), family and community/religious groups (19.5% each), and healthcare workers (18.7%). These results highlight the critical role of peer, spousal, familial, and communal ties in maternal well-being, with professional support playing a comparatively smaller role.

Financial support was the most reported type (26.8%), reflecting the economic burden of pregnancy and childcare. Physical (25.5%), emotional (23.9%), and informational (23.9%) support were also commonly received, underscoring their importance for maternal health. Overall, 41.1% of respondents expressed satisfaction with support received, while 38.1% were dissatisfied and 20.8% neutral, citing inconsistency, inadequate financial aid, and limited family

or healthcare engagement as key concerns. Notably, 25.7% reported never receiving consistent support, and 54% experienced neglect, highlighting critical gaps in structured maternal support systems.

Over half of respondents (54%) were unaware of the health benefits of social support, indicating a knowledge gap. While 42.1% agreed that strong support improves maternal outcomes, 39.2% disagreed and 18.7% were neutral. These mixed perceptions highlight the need for targeted health education to strengthen awareness of social support's role in reducing stress, enhancing well-being, and improving access to care. While 29.1% of respondents reported no health benefits from social support, others noted improved access to healthcare (25.2%), reduced stress (24.4%), and enhanced emotional well-being (21.3%). These findings underscore the role of financial, informational, and psychological support in promoting maternal health.

Respondents recommended several strategies to enhance social support and maternal care. Key measures included government policies such as subsidized services, maternity leave, and financial aid (28.1%), increased health awareness (24.7%), greater family involvement (24.2%), and stronger engagement from community and religious groups (23.1%). For healthcare services, priorities included expanding trained personnel (26.8%), maternal health campaigns (26.0%), affordable or free services (24.2%), and increased government funding (23.1%). These strategies highlight the need for structural, educational, and community-driven interventions to improve maternal health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The study highlights the vital role of social support in maternal health. Family, partners, friends, and community groups provide key support, though gaps in consistency and awareness remain. Financial assistance is most needed, reflecting the economic strain of pregnancy and childcare. While many recognized its benefits, others disagreed or were neutral, showing varied experiences. Addressing these gaps requires policy reforms, better funding, health education, and stronger community involvement to improve maternal outcomes and reduce morbidity and mortality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is need to create awareness in the study population on the need for physical, emotional, financial and informational support as well as consistency of all the support types for pregnant women in order to improve the experience and satisfaction level of pregnant women and nursing mothers in Calabar Metropolis.

Awareness programs for pregnant women should enhance the knowledge of pregnant women on the need for the various types of social support (financial, physical, emotional and informational). In order to enable them to be knowledge-equipped in seeking adequate support during the period of pregnancy.

Health facilities should always maintain the availability of trained healthcare professionals in adequate numbers, and Government should implement free or affordable maternal services in public health facilities as well as improved funding in order to enhance maternal health. Awareness should be made to improve family support for pregnant women as well as support from community and religious groups.

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